

THE ROLE OF DIFFUSION-WEIGHTED MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING IN THE STRATIFICATION OF MOLECULAR PROGNOSTIC BIOMARKERS IN BREAST CANCER

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ABSTRACT

Breast cancer is the most common malignant neoplasm among women worldwide. Modern oncology places special emphasis on the development of non-invasive methods for assessing the biological characteristics of tumors and predicting disease outcomes. The aim of this study was to investigate the potential of diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DW-MRI) in the stratification of molecular prognostic biomarkers in breast cancer. A total of 120 patients with morphologically confirmed breast cancer were examined. The results demonstrated a significant association between apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) values and the expression of molecular tumor markers, confirming the potential of DW-MRI as a valuable tool for personalized diagnosis and prognostic assessment of breast cancer.

Relevance. Breast cancer ranks first in the structure of oncological morbidity in women and remains one of the leading causes of death from malignant neoplasms [1, 2]. Despite significant advances in diagnosis and treatment of the disease, the prognosis is largely determined by the molecular biological characteristics of the tumor [3, 4].

Currently, the most important prognostic and predictive biomarkers are estrogen receptors (ER), progesterone receptors (PR), HER2/neu and the proliferative activity index Ki-67 [5, 6]. Determination of these indicators requires invasive biopsy and immunohistochemical examination [7].

One of the promising imaging methods is diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DW-MRI), which allows for the quantitative assessment of microstructural changes in tumor tissue by determining the measured diffusion coefficient (ADC) [8].

In recent years, radiomics and functional imaging have been rapidly developing, allowing for non-invasive assessment of tumor biological properties. One of the most promising methods is diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging, which reflects the degree of cellular density and microarchitecture of tumor tissue [9, 10].

Purpose of the study. To study the diagnostic value of diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging in stratifying molecular prognostic biomarkers in breast cancer.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted among 120 patients with morphologically confirmed breast cancer aged 32 to 76 years at the Fergana Regional

Oncology Hospital for the period 2022-2025. The average age of the subjects was 54.8 ± 1.2 years.

Distribution of patients by molecular subtypes: Luminal A – 38 patients (31.7%); Luminal B – 42 patients (35.0%); HER2-positive subtype – 21 patients (17.5%); triple-negative breast cancer – 19 patients (15.8%). All patients underwent the following: clinical examination; mammography; ultrasound examination of the mammary glands; magnetic resonance imaging with DWI; calculation of the measured diffusion coefficient (ADC); trephine biopsy; immunohistochemical examination of the tumor.

The following parameters were studied: ER expression; PR expression; HER2 status; Ki-67 index; tumor size; and grade of malignancy (G).

Statistical data processing was performed using SPSS Statistics 23.0. Mean values ($M \pm m$), Pearson correlation coefficients (r), and the level of statistical significance (p) were determined.

Results and discussion. Data analysis revealed significant differences in ADC values between different molecular subtypes of breast cancer. The lowest ADC values were found in patients with triple-negative breast cancer and HER2-positive tumors, reflecting the high cell density and aggressiveness of these subtypes. The highest ADC values were recorded for the Luminal A subtype, which is characterized by a more favorable prognosis.

The obtained results indicate a statistically significant decrease in the ADC coefficient as the aggressiveness of the tumor process increases (Table 1).

Table 1

ADC performance by tumor molecular subtype ($M \pm m$)

Molecular subtype	ADC ($\times 10^{-3}$ mm²/s)	Ki-67 (%)	p
Luminal A	1,18 \pm 0,05	14,6 \pm 1,3	<0,01
Luminal B	1,04 \pm 0,04	28,4 \pm 1,8	<0,01
HER2- ПОЗИТИВНЫЙ	0,92 \pm 0,03	37,8 \pm 2,1	<0,001
Triple negative	0,84 \pm 0,04	48,6 \pm 2,4	<0,001

A significant negative correlation was found between ADC values and the Ki-67 proliferation index, as well as the degree of tumor malignancy (Table 2).

Table 2

Correlation between DW-MRI parameters and molecular biomarkers

Indicator	r	p
ADC and Ki-67	-0,74	<0,001
ADC and grade of malignancy (G)	-0,69	<0,001
ADC and HER2 positivity	-0,58	<0,01
ADC and ER expression	0,62	<0,01
ADC and PR expression	0,57	<0,01

The obtained results demonstrate the high diagnostic value of diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging in assessing the biological properties of breast tumors. A

decreased ADC ratio was found to be associated with high cell density, increased proliferative activity, and aggressive tumor progression. The lowest ADC values were observed in patients with triple-negative and HER2-positive breast cancer subtypes.

The identified positive correlation between ADC and hormone receptor status confirms the possibility of using DW-MRI as an additional tool for non-invasive assessment of the tumor molecular phenotype.

The obtained data are consistent with the results of modern studies devoted to the use of radiomic technologies in oncology.

Conclusions:

1. Diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging is an informative method for non-invasive assessment of the biological characteristics of breast cancer;
2. Measured diffusion coefficient (ADC) values differ significantly between different molecular tumor subtypes;
3. Low ADC levels are associated with high proliferative activity of the tumor and poor prognosis of the disease;
4. A statistically significant negative correlation was revealed between ADC and the Ki-67 index ($r=-0.74$; $p<0.001$);
5. DW-MRI can be used as an additional tool for stratifying molecular prognostic biomarkers and personalizing treatment for patients with breast cancer;
6. The integrated use of MRI and immunohistochemical methods increases the accuracy of diagnosis and prognosis of the course of the disease.

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